

Hotspots and Novel Global Research Frontiers in Political Socialization: A Bibliometric Analysis

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Abstract

The burgeoning interest in the analysis of political socialization has paved the way for more studies in this area. For this study, 169 original research papers were obtained from the Web of Science database and were analyzed using the CiteSpace software. Parameters such as time span (2014-2022), visualization (depicting fully integrated networks), strict selection criteria (top 10%), node categories (institutions, author, subject, cited references; cited author, keywords, and journal), and pruning (pathfinder, network slicing) were utilized. The results indicate the most active contributors to the literature, with USA- and UK- based authors emerging as leading contributors in this research field. Over the years, the key focus areas have shifted, with "political socialization" and "participation" becoming increasingly important keywords in recent years. The evolution and growth of political socialization analysis are evident, underscoring the need for organizations and institutions to prepare for the integration of such techniques. The results offer valuable insights and trends that can guide future research directions and policy development in this sphere.

Keywords

Political socialization; bibliometric analysis; scientometrics; research trends; CiteSpace software

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Introduction

In the realm of political science, the concept of political socialization holds paramount importance, especially when considering the involvement of the youth in the activities of contemporary political parties. Political socialization refers to the intricate process through which individuals acquire political culture, ideologies, and behaviors that equip them to participate in political life effectively (Van Ditmars, 2023). The essence of this process finds root in myriad sources such as family, education, media, and political organizations, inter alia (Dahl and Stattin, 2016; Vila-Henninger, 2020). Notably, the youth, characterized by verve and ideational resilience, are a source of societal change and progress. In this context, understanding the dynamics of their political socialization within political parties is a matter of quintessence (Wang, 2016).

Historically, the political socialization of youth within party systems has been subject to extensive scrutiny. Almond and Verba's seminal work in 1963, *The Civic Culture*, illuminated the relationship between political culture and democratic stability, emphasizing the importance of socialization in inculcating democratic values. Fast-forward to the present day, contemporary studies such as Putnam's *Bowling Alone* in 2000 illustrate the challenges faced by political socialization in a world increasingly marked by civic disengagement (Bos et al., 2022). However, despite an extensive body of literature, several lacunae remain. Most conspicuously, the literature lacks exhaustive bibliometric studies that elucidate the difficulties, causes, and countermeasures of political socialization among political party youth. Further, little is known about how evolving technological and social landscapes have influenced this phenomenon (Cardenas, 2020).

Concomitantly, political party youth today face significant challenges that may impede their socialization process. From information overload to ideological echo chambers on social media platforms, the modern-day milieu throws a spanner in the works (Ferrin et al., 2020; Pedraza and Perry, 2020). Grappling with the convoluted political landscape, youth, often stuck in information bubbles, may struggle to discern nuanced political thought, impacting their ability to meaningfully contribute within party systems. Thereupon, it is incumbent upon scholars and policymakers to address these issues through empirically grounded and methodologically rigorous research (Lay, 2017; Disi Pavlic and Mardones, 2021).

Within this context, the present study seeks to bridge these gaps. Employing bibliometric analysis, a methodological approach that quantitatively analyzes academic literature, this study intends to provide a comprehensive overview of the difficulties, causes, and countermeasures of political socialization among contemporary political party youth. For this purpose, data was extracted from the Web of Science Core Collections (WOSCC), compiling a nine-year data set. Utilizing an array of keywords (as depicted in Table 1), a pool of 128 articles was initially retrieved. Upon rigorous screening and refining, 100 articles, ranging from 2014 to 2022, were selected for the final analysis.

Furthermore, to elucidate and assess the literature visually, CiteSpace visualization, a revered tool in social network analysis, was utilized (Wang et al., 2022). Through the use of CiteSpace, the study aims to discern patterns, themes, and networks among authors, institutions, and publications in the field. This analytical technique, originally developed by Chen Chaomei, has found global application in natural sciences and social research alike. Collectively, this study is poised to make several contributions. It aims to synthesize the existing literature, to identify gaps, and provide recommendations for addressing the challenges faced by political party youth in their socialization process. Moreover, by applying bibliometric analysis and CiteSpace visualization, it seeks to lay the groundwork for future researchers and policymakers striving to foster an engaged and informed youth within political parties. The whole framework is depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The flowchart outlining the tasks of this study

Methodology

Since Web of Science is frequently regarded as a remarkable data source for bibliometric research (Azam et al., 2021), we used information obtained from the Web of Science Core Collections (WOSCC). To find the most pertinent works in the area of political socialization, we investigated multiple keywords to identify the articles and extract the data. The complete list of keywords included: political socialization, political party youth, political difficulties, political causes, political countermeasures, political science, youth politics, political education, political behavior, or political sociology. The complete query we used is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Criteria for the WOS data extraction process.

Criterion	Code	Resulting articles
1	(("political socialization" OR "political party youth" OR "political difficulties" OR "political causes" OR "political countermeasures") AND ("political science" OR "youth politics" OR "political education" OR "political behavior" OR "political sociology"))	128
2	only original articles	125
3	removed early access and book chap	115
4	2014-2022	100

The initial query resulted in 128 articles that included one of the keywords in the title, abstract, or keywords fields. After selecting only original articles, the number of articles decreased to 125. After removing early-access articles and book chapters, the number decreased to 115 articles. Finally, after requesting only articles published between 2014 and 2022 the final number of articles decreased to 100.

CiteScore was used for data collection, primary analysis, and visual inspection (Puce et al., 2022). We began our analysis by referencing a basic CS text instruction and developing a proposal for a project called "political socialization" using the detailed WOS list. We also attempted to use other research collections in addition to WOSCC, but our selection was limited by the CiteScore software and we decided to conduct our analysis on the 100 articles extracted from WOSCC. The next steps included defining the period of time under analysis (2014 to 2022), using a one-year slicer co-authorship, establishing the visualizations (displaying the cumulative network), and defining additional parameters: the precise assortment requirements (the top 10%), the node structure (author, institution, category, credible source cited; cited researcher, keyword research), the pruning (including the exploration and slicing channel), as well as the selection procedure (which included the top 10 percent).

The accumulation of a network and data presenting authors, organizations, and nations with multi-article publications, journals, and authors who have been referenced twice or more was essential to CiteScore's functionality, as was the examination of co-occurrences of one or more occurrences. The visual outcomes of this study's data and network correlations are presented. Since the current CiteScore-based study pinpoints the most pertinent research subjects, hotspots, and constraints in political socialization analysis research, it can greatly aid future research in this area.

Co-authorship in political socialization research

Researchers may use CiteSpace to analyze and display data from academic publications. The field of scientometrics, which attempts to measure and evaluate developments in the fields of science and technology, makes extensive use of bibliometric methods (Jiménez-García et al., 2020).

Co-authorship in political socialization research. Collaboration on the national and institutional levels is necessary in the social sciences for the analysis of massive data sets, representing an example of scientific cooperation (Yu et al., 2017). Finding other specialists in the subject from all across the globe may be difficult, but studies of co-authorship, such as the one presented here, in the field of political socialization and analysis, might be of use in this endeavor (Zhang et al., 2021).

Figure 2 showcases a collaborative endeavor of several researchers who have contributed significantly to the body of knowledge of political socialization and analysis research (Xing et al., 2023). The size of each node is directly related to the cumulative volume of articles generated by the respective authors. When the collaboration frequency between authors increases, the strength of their connection is enhanced. The visual representation features different colors to denote the age of publications, with a blue background representing older research and a yellow one indicating more recent publications (Liu et al., 2015).

The largest sub-network, led by John Holbein, constitutes a total of six nodes. Additional significant contributors to this group include Jens Olav Dahlgard, Kasper Hansen, and Elias Dinas. The second-largest group is headed by Amy Erica Smith and comprises four nodes, including contributions from Sven Oskarsson.

The data in Table 2 indicate the 10 most prolific writers, the total number of articles they contributed to, and the years in which those articles were published.

Figure 2. Author co-authorship analysis in political socialization and analysis research**Table 2.** The ten most prolific authors in the political socialization and analysis field

No.	Count	Year	Author
1	3	2020	Holbein, John B
2	3	2017	Dahlggaard, Jens Olav
3	2	2017	Hansen, Kasper M
4	2	2014	Dinas, Elias
5	2	2017	Smith, Amy Erica
6	2	2014	Oskarsson, Sven
7	2	2014	Neundorf, Anja
8	2	2017	Lay, J Celeste
9	2	2017	Boonen, Joris
10	2	2014	Smets, Kaat

Institution co-authorship in political socialization research. We get a peek at the intricate author-co-authorship network of organizations involved in the study of political socialization and analysis in Figure 3. The number of papers generated by each university is represented by its size, and the width of each connecting line shows the extent of institutional cooperation. The universities that have published four or more articles are highlighted in Figure 3, which reveals a cooperative network supported by three main subnetworks dispersed geographically and a collection of other institutions scattered over great distances.

The collaboration network demonstrates the reach of I-Shou University, which has formed academic alliances with 14 institutions, some of which are not depicted in the provided figures. On a similar note, Tomsk State University has already forged strong publication relations with six institutions, including Tulane University. To gain a deeper understanding of Figure 3, **Error! Reference source not found.** provides a quick summary of the top ten universities from different countries, ordered by the total number of papers they published on the topic of political socialization.

Table 3. Analysis of political socialization institutions and CiteScore research productivity

No.	Count	Year	Institution
1	3	2016	I-Shou Univresity
2	3	2019	Tomsk State University
3	3	2017	Tulane University
4	3	2019	Harvard University
5	3	2017	Copenhagen Business School
6	3	2014	University of Nottingham
7	3	2017	Iowa State University
8	2	2018	Princeton University
9	2	2020	College of Wooster
10	2	2014	Uppsala University

Figure 3. Research on political socialization and analysis produced jointly by institutions

Country co-authorship in political socialization research. Through a comprehensive study of co-author networks of studies done inside particular countries, Figure 4 provides an illuminating glimpse of the worldwide landscape of research on political socialization and analysis. The greater the size of a country's circle, the greater its share of global publications. Meanwhile, the closeness of the nodes and the density of the linkages demonstrate the breadth of international cooperation. The importance of a node is indicated by the size of the purple circle.

Figure 4. Political socialization and analytic research CiteScore map of country authorship

In total, Figure 4 includes 45 networks, exhibiting a density of 0.12. It sheds light on the geographical spread of research, with notable contributions stemming from Europe (England, Spain, Italy, Switzerland, Netherlands), North America (USA), Oceania (Australia), Asia (Taiwan, People's Republic of China), and South America (Brazil). **Error! Reference source not found.** lists the top countries in terms of research findings connected to political socialization and analysis. This table is based on CiteScore analysis and is an effort to offer a more thorough analysis. In the table below, we can see the total number of scientific publications published in this area, broken down by country, along with the years in which they were released.

In 2014, USA dominated the research landscape in political socialization and analysis, with a total of 35 published articles. England follows, contributing nine articles in the same year. Meanwhile, Spain and Russia have demonstrated considerable research activity, with five publications each in 2016 and 2019, respectively. The landscape further broadened to include Asia, with Taiwan securing the fifth position with four publications in 2016. Similarly, Denmark added to the European contribution with four works in 2017. Further down the ranking, Belgium, Switzerland, and Sweden each account for three research outputs, published in 2017, 2015, and 2014 respectively.

Table 4. Top nations in terms of research output in the field of political socialization

No.	Count	Year	Country
1	35	2014	USA
2	9	2014	UK
3	5	2016	Spain
4	5	2019	Russia
5	4	2016	Taiwan
6	4	2017	Denmark
7	3	2017	Belgium
8	3	2015	Switzerland
9	3	2014	Sweden

Co-citation in political socialization research

Figure 5 provides an intricate network graph representing the citation relationships existing between different journals. The size of a node in this context is directly correlated to the total number of citations an article from the respective journal has garnered. Additionally, the proximity between two nodes is an indicator of their interconnectedness, which in essence denotes how frequently articles from these two journals cite each other.

Figure 5. Co-citation network analysis of journals publishing political socialization research

To provide a more tangible overview of the domain, **Error! Reference source not found.** illustrates the ten most productive journals within political socialization and analysis research, as delineated by the CiteScore analysis. The table presents details about each journal's contribution in terms of research publications in this field, along with the year these articles were published.

Table 5. Table caption Calibri 10, left-aligned, at 1.15 rows.

No.	Count	Year	Journal
1	57	2014	American Political Science Review
2	54	2014	Journal of Politics
3	53	2014	American Journal of Political Science
4	41	2014	Political Behavior
5	34	2014	Political Psychology
6	28	2015	British Journal of Political Science
7	27	2014	Public Opinion Quarterly
8	26	2014	Annual Review of Political Science
9	26	2014	American Sociological Review
10	25	2014	Political Research Quarterly

Topping the list is the *American Political Science Review*, with a total of 57 articles. *Journal of Politics* follows closely behind in the second spot, contributing 54 articles. The third spot is occupied by the *American Journal of Political Science*, with 53 publications. Further down the line, *Political Behavior* and *Political Psychology* make significant contributions with 41 and 34 articles, respectively. The analysis also highlights the role of the *British Journal of Political Science*, with 28 articles. Rounding off the list are *Public Opinion Quarterly*, the *Annual Review of Political Science*, the *American Sociological Review*, and *Political Research Quarterly*, publishing 27, 26, 26, and 25 articles respectively. The number of articles published in these journals underscores their role in publishing research on political socialization. These journals serve as primary repositories for the latest findings in this area, making them invaluable resources for both academics and professionals interested in the field.

Figure 6. Map of co-cited documents in the field of political socialization.

Document co-citation in political socialization research. The topic of political socialization is largely grounded in a rich array of scholarly publications. The essence of co-citation within these works is proof of their importance. For a nuanced understanding of a domain's structure and developmental trajectory, as exemplified by political socialization analysis training, it's crucial to focus on key studies that provide a foundational backdrop for an article's co-citation network. In Figure 6, created using CiteScore, nodes represent different data sources. All sources cited four or more times are represented by the first author's name and the year of publication. The links between nodes, depicted by arrows, represent instances where one source cites another.

To provide further clarity, Table 6 lists the top seven most frequently cited documents, along with relevant details like total citation count, year of publication, and corresponding reference. The first position is occupied by “A Generational Model of Political Learning”, the article published by Bartels and Jackman in 2014 in *Electoral Studies*. The next position is occupied by “Politics across Generations: Family Transmission Reexamined”, published by Jennings et al in 2009 in the *Journal of Politics*.

Table 6. Top 5 articles according to citations.

No.	Count	Year	Document	Reference
1	4	2014	Bartels LM, 2014, ELECT STUD, V33, P7, DOI 10.1016/j.electstud.2013.06.004	(Bartels & Jackman, 2014)
2	3	2009	Jennings MK, 2009, J POLIT, V71, P782, DOI 10.1017/S0022381609090719	(Jennings et al., 2009)
3	2	2013	Zeglovits E, 2013, J YOUTH STUD, V16, P1084, DOI 10.1080/13676261.2013.793785	(Zeglovits & Zandonella, 2013)
4	2	2013	Blais A, 2013, COMP POLIT STUD, V46, P95, DOI 10.1177/0010414012453032	(Blais & Rubenson, 2013)
5	2	2015	Ojeda C, 2015, AM SOCIOL REV, V80, P1150, DOI 10.1177/0003122415606101	(Ojeda & Hatemi, 2015)

Author co-citation in political socialization research. An analysis of author co-citations can provide insights into the research themes and areas of interest of authors within a field. It can also indicate the frequency with which particular authors and researchers are referenced in the field's literature. Each node in Figure 7 represents a separate author, and the line between any two writers in the figure represents the co-citation connection between them. Authors that have received seven or more citations are highlighted in the figure.

Error! Reference source not found. includes the most often cited authors in political socialization, as determined by a CiteScore analysis. The high citation numbers of these authors underline the significance of their contributions. Leading the list is Sidney Verba, with 27 citations, followed by Mark Jennings, with 23 citations. Other prominent authors in the list are Eric Plutzer, with 15 citations, Richard Niemi, with 13 citations (Neundorf et al., 2016), and David Sears, with 12 citations. Authors like David Campbell, Herbert Hyman, John Alford, and Russell Dalton have also been frequently cited in the field.

It is widely agreed that these writers made substantial contributions to the literature on political socialization. This table provides a concise overview of the most influential scholars whose studies on the issue of political socialization and analysis have been mentioned extensively in the academic literature.

Figure 7. Most cited authors in political socialization research**Table 7.** Most cited authors in political socialization research

No.	Count	Year	Name of Cited Author
1	27	2014	Verba, S.
2	23	2014	Jennings, M.K.
3	15	2014	Plutzer, E.
4	13	2014	Niemi, R.G.
5	12	2017	Sears, D.O.
6	10	2016	Campbell, D.E.
7	8	2016	Hyman, H.
8	8	2014	Alford, J.R.
9	8	2016	Dalton, R.J.

Co-occurrence in political socialization research

Analysis of keyword co-occurrence might offer some insights into articles' underlying ideas. Keywords that are often used together may be used to infer trending themes, leading to the formation of a knowledge map of keyword co-occurrence. Figure 8 depicts each node as a separate keyword with connections between them shown by lines.

Error! Reference source not found. displays the 15 most popular terms used in studies of political socialization and analysis, as determined by content analysis. Across all 31 studies, "political socialization" was mentioned most often in 2014. In 2016, "attitude" was mentioned 13 times, "family" was mentioned 11 times, and "civic education" was mentioned 8 times (10 times in 2015). Words like "engagement" (9 times in 2016), "democracy" (7 times in 2016), "behavior" (6 times in 2014),

"education" (6 times in 2016), and "civic engagement" (6 times in 2016) also come up in conversation often (6 times in 2015).

Keywords like "political socialization," "civic education," "family impact," and "democratic involvement" indicate important topics and areas of attention in the study of political socialization and analysis.

Figure 8. CiteScore keyword analysis for studies of political socialization

Table 8. Frequently used terms in studies of political socialization.

No.	Count	Year	Keyword
1	31	2014	political socialization
2	18	2016	participation
3	13	2016	attitude
4	11	2016	family
5	10	2015	civic education
6	9	2016	engagement
7	7	2016	democracy
8	6	2014	behavior
9	6	2016	education
10	6	2015	civic engagement

New frontiers

Figure 9 depicts a new grouping of publications, with the size of each grouping reflecting the number of articles included in that group. The silhouette numbers reflect the many potential cluster configurations. The significance of a silhouette will determine how well it will cluster. For each cluster,

the stated year is the median year of publication for the publications included inside that cluster. The core of a cluster analysis built from recent data will reveal emerging tendencies inside the cluster.

Figure 9. Most cited reference clusters for political socialization

Table 9 displays the 12 most often mentioned reference clusters. Cluster-ID 0 is the most dynamic cluster: it has 25 nodes, with a median year of 2017, and a silhouette score of 0.805. The generational effects of many social phenomena are the primary focus of research in this field. At the 0.005 level, the log-likelihood ratio (LLR) for all of the categories associated with this cluster is 9.69, with generation, social interaction, cross-strait ties, parent, and American standing out as the strongest (LLR: 4.81 at 0.05 level). Further, parent, American, and dynamics are the most highly related mutual-information (MI) labels to this cluster, with values of 0.22 each. This clustering suggests that in 2017, academics studying generational effects focused on characteristics such as social interaction, cross-strait interactions, parental figures, and U.S. citizens.

An emerging area of research is "age cohort and attitude towards democracy" (Cluster-ID 11). With a size of 7, a silhouette score of 0.969, and an association year of 2020, Cluster-ID 11 is a young cluster (Grasso et al., 2019; Smets & Neundorf, 2014). Some of the most studied topics in this group are age-cohort, attitudes towards democracy, political involvement, non-cognitive abilities, and education. The high average LLR ratings for these issues suggest they are the most relevant and important ones to study: age cohort and attitude towards democracy (7.54, 0.01). Other important topics to investigate in this set are political engagement (7.54, 0.01), non-cognitive abilities (7.54, 0.01), and schooling (4.82, 0.05). The most popular labels in this cluster had MI scores of 0.04, further highlighting the significance of these words in the present research. Within the context of political

engagement, this new group is particularly interesting in terms of generational makeup, political stance, and similar topics.

Table 9. A summary of the top 12 clusters

ID	Size	Silhouette	Mean (Year)	Label (LLR)	Label (MI)
0	25	0.805	2017	Generation (9.69, 0.01) Social contact (6.05, 0.05) Cross-strait relations (6.05, 0.05) Parent (4.81, 0.05) American (4.81, 0.05)	Parent American Dynamics
1	21	0.891	2018	Issue publics (4.04, 0.05) Vote choice (4.04, 0.05) Socioeconomic status (4.04, 0.05) communication (4.04, 0.05) Left-right (4.04, 0.05)	Issue publics Vote choice Socioeconomic status
2	21	0.844	2018	Instrumental variables (5.45, 0.05) Party system fragmentation (5.45, 0.05) Dual-process model (5.45, 0.05) EU parliament elections (5.45, 0.05) Sunflower movement (5.45, 0.05)	Instrumental variables Party system fragmentation
3	18	0.93	2015	Reciprocal effects (6.78, 0.01) Political consumerism (6.78, 0.01) Gender differences (6.78, 0.01) Civic engagement (6.78, 0.01) Communication mediation (6.78, 0.01)	Reciprocal effects Political consumerism
4	18	0.96	2014	Cross-level interaction (4.81, 0.05) Cohort analysis (4.81, 0.05) Multilevel modeling (4.81, 0.05) Democratic maturity (4.81, 0.05) Turnout (4.81, 0.05)	Cross-level interaction Cohort analysis
5	18	0.899	2017	Transnational politics (5.56, 0.05) Mom (5.56, 0.05) Political learning (5.56, 0.05) Les (5.56, 0.05) Mass media (5.56, 0.05)	Transnational politics Mom Political learning
6	16	0.904	2018	Attitude (8.96, 0.005) Competition (4.45, 0.05) Asian american politics (4.45, 0.05) Protest (4.45, 0.05) Inference (4.45, 0.05)	Competition Asian american politics
7	16	0.937	2018	Political socialization (4.44, 0.05) Voter turnout (4.2, 0.05) Authoritarianism (3.83, 0.10) Birth order (3.83, 0.10) Economic values (3.83, 0.10)	Authoritarianism Birth order Economic values
8	14	0.976	2018	Affective polarization (5.94, 0.05) Nationalism (5.94, 0.05) Social sorting (5.94, 0.05)	Affective polarization Nationalism

ID	Size	Silhouette	Mean (Year)	Label (LLR)	Label (MI)
9	11	0.951	2017	Political socialization (6.06, 0.05) Partnership (4.2, 0.05) Certification (4.2, 0.05) Political socialization (4.2, 0.05) Diffusion (4.2, 0.05)	Partnership Certification Political socialization
10	10	0.961	2020	Field research (5.8, 0.05) Immigration enforcement (5.8, 0.05) political attitudes (5.8, 0.05) Entrapment (5.8, 0.05) Black (5.8, 0.05)	Field research Immigration enforcement
11	7	0.969	2020	Age cohort (7.54, 0.01) Attitude toward democracy (7.54, 0.01) Political participation (7.54, 0.01) Non-cognitive skills (7.54, 0.01) Education (4.82, 0.05)	Age cohort Attitude toward democracy

New patterns of political engagement and analysis are identified in our analysis, as indicated by the top 25 keywords for political socialization, shown in Table 10. The table also includes estimates of growth from 2014 to 2022. The overall time is shown by the blue line, while the length of the burst is shown by the red line.

Table 10. Top keywords with citation bursts

Keywords	Year	Strength	Begin	End	2014 - 2022
participation	2016	1.79	2017	2018	
political socialization	2021	1.78	2021	2022	
parent	2016	1.77	2016	2017	
socialization	2017	1.68	2017	2017	
turnout	2018	1.64	2018	2018	
political behavior	2021	1.18	2021	2022	
political participation	2021	1.18	2021	2022	
political engagement	2021	1.18	2021	2022	
value	2021	1.18	2021	2022	
ideology	2016	1.16	2016	2016	
political efficacy	2017	1.12	2017	2017	
lesson	2014	1.11	2014	2015	
mass media	2018	1.09	2018	2018	
top down	2018	1.09	2018	2018	
time	2018	1.09	2018	2018	
public opinion	2020	1.06	2020	2020	
support	2020	1.06	2020	2020	
political culture	2020	1.06	2020	2020	
policy	2020	1.06	2020	2020	
personality	2020	1.06	2020	2020	
childhood	2020	1.06	2020	2020	

satisfaction with democracy	2020	1.06	2020	2020	
school	2020	1.06	2020	2020	
voter	2020	1.06	2020	2020	
communication	2015	1.05	2015	2015	

Based on our analyses presented above, we can identify three major research areas in which studies of political socialization will attempt to push against the boundaries of our knowledge.

Political Behavior. This refers to the actions and attitudes of individuals and groups concerning politics and governance. Political behavior encompasses a wide range of phenomena including voting patterns, political discussions, political identities, and the influence of social factors on political attitudes. (Vila-Henninger, 2020) For youth members of political parties, understanding their political behavior is critical in determining how they integrate and contribute to the political culture of their organizations (Kirdjashkin V, 2020). Novel research into political behavior among youth can include studies into the influence of social media on political identities, how educational background shapes political attitudes, and what behavioral traits influence their commitment to party ideologies (Fox & Lawless, 2014; Garcia-Castanon, 2018).

Political Participation. This refers to the involvement of individuals in political processes and activities. Common forms of political participation include voting, attending political rallies, contributing to political campaigns, and engaging in political discussions. For contemporary political party youth, their level of political participation is indicative of their integration and commitment to the political process (Chang, 2019; Sugie, 2015; Vidal, 2018). A bibliometric analysis of political participation can involve examining historical trends of youth participation in various political activities and identifying barriers that limit the political participation of youth. This can also encompass novel digital means of participation such as online activism and e-voting, which can be particularly relevant to contemporary youth (Kumler & Whittaker, 2020; van Ingen & van der Meer, 2016; Yin, 2022).

Political Engagement. This concept goes beyond participation by encompassing not only actions but also the level of interest and concern individuals have toward political matters. Political engagement includes staying informed about political issues, discussing politics, and taking actions that influence political outcomes (Hatemi & Ojeda, 2021; Martinez-Cousinou et al., 2021; Shcherbinin, 2019). For youth in political parties, their engagement is key to understanding their willingness to be actively involved in shaping party policies and political outcomes. Researching political engagement can involve analyzing how youth interact with political content online, the impact of civic education on engagement, and the role of youth in shaping policy through their engagement (Fuertes, 2019; Mulder, 2023; Xiaoxin, 2018).

Conclusions and future research

The study sought to assess the knowledge landscape of political socialization using a bibliometric approach. The application of CiteScore for visual analysis identified emerging patterns and trends in this field, offering valuable insights for future studies and potential expansion. A shift in research focus is observable, with "political socialization" and "participation" becoming hot keywords. These trends suggest potential future research directions and can inform organizations and institutions preparing to incorporate political socialization analysis and analysis techniques.

The findings underline the value of visual bibliometric tools such as CiteScore in enhancing the understanding and interpretation of complex datasets. Although the study relied solely on the WOSCC for obtaining research articles, we recommend including more bibliometric databases, such as Scopus or PubMed, for a more comprehensive analysis

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